

ISOLATION OF PHENOL DEGRADING BACTERIA FROM INDUSTRIAL WASTE

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ABSTRACT : Phenol is one of the most common pollutants present in the industrial waste. It create many health problem in human as well as in many other animals. In this present study three different samples were collected from the Dada Nagar industrial area Kanpur, from these sample we have isolated 15 different bacteria. These bacteria were subjected for the phenol tolerance test. From these bacteria we were isolated four bacteria (DI-2, DI-3, SWD-2, DFS-2) who have good level of phenol tolerance. All four bacteria were subjected for comparative phenol degradation study. We found that all four bacteria have the capacity to degrade phenol but the most efficient bacteria for phenol degrading was DFS-2. These four bacteria were identified as DI-2 (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), DI-3 (*Pseudomonas citronellolis*), SWD-2 (*Klebsiella spp.*), SDF-2 (*Pseudomonas putida*).

Key words : Isolation, Phenol degrading bacteria, Industrial waste.

INTRODUCTION

Phenol is a crystalline colorless substance, soluble in organic solvents and water. It is found in nature as well as manmade. It has common commercial uses in industry like-production of cresols, alkylphenols, xlenols, aniline, phenolic resins, and other compounds, coal, oil refinery and metallurgic. Phenol is also used in explosives, pesticides, dyes and textiles. It is the first chemical use as disinfectant on the name of carboic acid and it is also use as a reagent in chemical analysis. It is synthesizes from coal tar.

As we discuss above many of the industry use phenol so the waste product of all these will contain phenol and by these phenol environment will get polluted. As we know phenol has antimicrobial property so only few microorganisms can grow and those who can grow in presence of phenol (Stormer,1908 and Dean-Ross,1989), only they can degrade phenol (Nair *et al.*, 2008).

Phenol has severe health affect (Deichmann & Keplinger,1981 and Deichmann *et al.*,1944), it can cause genetic disorder as well as many skin, brain, eye kidney, liver related disuse. phenol is reported to be lethal for humans (Kumaran and Paruchuri, 1996). The present study deals with the identification of phenol degrading bacteria and there comparative study for phenol degradation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sample collection : Sewage samples (both sediment and water) were collected in sterile polypropylene bottles from Dadar nagar industrial area Kanpur of January,2016. The samples were carried to the laboratory under ice cover.

Isolation and preservation of bacteria : One gram of sediment samples were re-suspended in sterile peptone water (0.85%). One milliliter of suspended sediment and raw sewage were added in 10 ml of MM1 broth containing 100 ppm phenol. The broths were then incubated at 30°C under shaking condition (100 rpm) for two weeks. One loop-full culture from the inoculated broth was then restreaked on R2A agar, incubated for another 7th days and the colonies different in morphology was picked up using tooth pick and re-inoculated in TSB broth with another 7th days incubation. Then the cultures in the broth were preserved in 15% glycerol stock at -40°C.

Purity checking of the isolates : The revived broth cultures were streaked on to R₂A agar plates and incubated at 28°C for 4-7th days for pure culture. Plates showing more than one type of colony, each colony type was further streaked and this continued till a single colony type were obtained. The single colony from plate was again inoculated in TSB. After heavy growth of bacteria in TSB, one loop of broth culture was transferred in MM 1 broth supplemented with phenol (200 ppm).

Growth of isolated bacteria on different concentration of phenol : Isolated bacteria were checked for the tolerance to the phenol. For the assay, a fixed amount of bacteria were transferred into conical flasks containing 5 0 ml of MM2 broths and 200,

400, 600, 800 ppm concentrations of phenol. Four conical flasks were kept as negative control that received different levels (200, 400, 600, 800 ppm) of phenol, but no bacteria. All the flasks were then incubated at 30°C for 48 hrs.

Preparation of standard graph phenol : Stock solution of phenol of 20 mg/ml was prepared by suspending 40 mg of phenol in 2 ml of distilled water. From these stock solution we have prepare 50,100,150, 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500 ppm phenol solution. 400 µl sodium bicarbonate (0.05 N). Then 400 µl of amino antipyrine solution (0.6%) was added and mixed well. After that 400 µl of potassium ferric cyanide solution (2.4%) as added and mixed well. After 15 min of incubation the developed colour was measured by reading absorbance of sample and standards against the distilled water blank at 500 nm in UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Phenol concentration was estimated using a scanning UV-Visible spectrophotometer (SISTRONICS AU-2603). Phenol was estimated by measuring the absorbance at 500 nm

Spectrophotometric estimation of phenol degradation : Biodegradation of phenol was examined using individual bacterial strains in MM1 medium and 500 ppm phenol was addwd to the medium after 7th days of inculcation bacterial sample was centrifuge to remove the bacterial cell and media were use for identification of phenol concentration in the medium. Phenol concentrations present in the broth were measured spectrophotometrically to assess the consumption of phenol by the isolated bacteria. Phenol concentration was measured at wavelength 500 nm. Suitable aliquots of sample were clarified by centrifugation and the clear sample were treated by adding 400 µl sodium bicarbonate (0.05 N). Then 400 µl of amino antipyrine solution (0.6%) was added and mixed well. After that 400 µl of potassium ferric cyanide solution (2.4%) as added and mixed well. After 15 min of incubation the developed colour was measured by reading absorbance of sample and standards against the distilled water blank at 500 nm in UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Phenol concentration was estimated using a scanning UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Sistrionics AU-2603). Phenol was estimated by measuring the absorbance at 500 nm (Michael Dennis *et al.*,1951).

Identification of phenol degrading bacteria bacteria : Identification of phenol degrading bacteria was done by the help of various biochemical tests like Gram staining, Motility, Capsule formation, Spore, Flagella, Catalase, Oxidase, MR, VP, indole, citrate, urease, Nitrate reduction H₂S, Gas, PYR, CAMP and Gelatin hydrolysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isolation and preservation of bacteria : Isolation of bacteria from sample were done by serial dilution method. Total 15 different bacterial colony were observed. Then these bacterial colony were streaked R2A agar plate and named as DI-1, DI-2, DI-3, DI-4, DI-5, SWD-1, SWD-2, SWD-3, SWD-4, SWD-5, SWD-6, DSF-1, DSF-2, DSF-3, DSF-4.

Table. 1 Growth of isolated bacteria on different concentration of phenol.

Name of bacterial sample	Phenol concentration (ppm)			
	200	400	600	800
DI-1	++	+	-	-
DI-2	+++	+++	+++	+++
DI-3	+++	+++	+++	+++
DI-4	+++	++	++	+
DI-5	++	++	-	-
SWD-1	+++	+++	++	+
SWD-2	+++	+++	+++	+++
SWD-3	-	-	-	-
SWD-4	+	-	-	-
SWD-5	++	++	-	-
SWD-6	+++	++	+	-
DSF-1	++	++	-	-
DSF-2	+++	+++	+++	+++
DSF-3	-	-	-	-
DSF-4	++	+	-	-

Table. 2 Degradation of phenol at 500 ppm concentration.

S.	Bacterial sample	OD at 500 nm	Concentration of phenol in uninoculated media (ppm)	Total phenol concentration in the media (ppm)	Total degradation of phenol after 7 th day of inoculation (ppm)
1.	DI-2	.125	200	55	145
2.	DI-3	.367	200	175	25
3.	SWD-2	.200	200	95	105
4.	DSF-2	.06	200	25	175

Preparation of standard graph phenol : The absorption of the sample was taken by spectrophotometer and standard graph were prepared.

Spectrophotometric estimation of phenol degradation : After checking the phenol tolerance of the bacteria we were selected four bacteria who have good level of tolerance to the phenol. Then these bacteria were used to check the phenol degradation.

There was a study on degradation of phenol by native microorganisms isolated from coke processing wastewater. It was observed that maximum degradation of 33.46% occurred in cultures placed at 30°C for 6hr (Chakraborty *et al.*,2010). (Sheeja and Murugesan,2002) has find out Aromatic hydrocarbons are not as readily biodegradable as the normal and branched. But alkanes, they are somewhat more easily degradable than the alicyclic hydrocarbons. Many of these compounds are toxic and some are known or suspected carcinogens.

The research finding suggest that industrial waste contains four different bacteria DI-2 (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), DI-3 (*Pseudomonas citronellolis*), SWD-2 (*Klebsiella spp.*), SDF-2 (*Pseudomonas putida*) for the degradation phenol. Among these four bacteria SDF-2 (*Pseudomonas putida*) has maximum ability for the degradation of phenol.

Table. 3 Biochemical test of different bacteria.

Biochemical test	DI-2	DI-3	SWD-2	SDF-2
Gram staining	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Shape	Rod	Rod	Rod	rod
Motility	+ve	+ve	-ve	+ve
Capsule	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Spore	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Flagella	Single			
Catalase	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve
Oxidase	+ve	+ve		+ve
MR	-ve	-ve	--ve	-ve
VP	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve
OF (Oxidative/fermentative)	Oxidative	Oxidative	Fermentative	
Oxidative				
Indole	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Citrate	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve
Urease	-ve		+ve	-ve
Nitrate reduction	+ve		+ve	-ve
H ₂ S	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Gas	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve
Gelatin hydrolysis	+ve	+ve	-ve	+ve
Fermentation test				
Glucose	-ve	+ve	+ve	+ve
Inulin	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve
Lactose	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve
Maltose	-ve	+ve	+ve	+ve
Mannitol	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve
Sorbitol	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve
	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	<i>P.citronellolis</i>	<i>Klebsiella</i>	<i>P.putida</i>

Fig. 1 Standard graph of phenol.

Fig. 2 Phenol degradation graph.

There was no research available which have the comparative analysis of phenol degradation by these bacteria. This study can help in phenol remediation. The study of Scheiben bogen *et al.* (1994) and Mulligan *et al.* (2000) suggest that *Pseudomonas* spp. Bacteria involve in bioremediation. So that we can use single bacteria or the mixture of these bacteria for the treatment of phenol contaminated industrial effluent. These bacteria can degrade phenol along with other organic compound. One must question that the comparison of phenol degradation was measured up to 7th days only. The capacity of bacteria for phenol degradation can increase or decrease by increasing the time period of incubation.

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